

Augmenting people's lives using Artificial Intelligence

Srinidhi (Srini) Ravindranath^a

^a *CEO TECK GURU, LLC Las Vegas Nevada*

Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Medical coding today transforms healthcare diagnosis, procedures, medical services and equipment into universal medical alphanumeric codes

How it works today:

- Current practices take 20 min per chart
- Accuracy of 65-75%
- Constrained by human limitations
- Hidden heuristic for decision making (human thought)
- Cost and lead time in processing denied claims
- Provider follow up for chart completion and denial management

2. Aim

Deep Neural Networks in service of hospitals to efficiently predict and categorize patients into specialized billing related codes

80% of charts will be programmatically done in milliseconds

Machine based scalability

Transparent and auditable review to support coding decision.

98% accuracy of predicted diagnosis related groups

3. Material and methods

Our AI platform was trained on over 100 million patient records to build a knowledge map of disease progression, local coding practices and denial rates.

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4. Results

Classifiers had 98% accuracy of predicted diagnosis related groups for a given hospitalization event. 80% time improvement compared to expert human coders.

5. Conclusions

In use at over 200 hospitals in the USA after a two year long pilot to test efficacy.

6. Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Deep Neural Networks.

Author biography

Srinidhi (Srini) Ravindranath Srinidhi (Srini) Ravindranath, CEO TECK GURU, LLC.